

Extraction of Fertiliser Grade Potassium Salts from Tsokar Lake[†]

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Separation of sylvinitic and schoenitic potassic salts from mixed salts of Tsokar lake has been studied at 26, 30, 34 and 38°. It has been established that 34° acts as boundary line for separation of sylvinitic and schoenitic potassic salts. It has also been established that sylvinitic potassic salts on processing give potassium chloride of 98% purity; and schoenitic potassic salts on processing give a mixture of potassium sulphate and schoenite with 38-39% K₂O which are well-suited potassic fertilisers.

MIXED salts from Tsokar lake brine has high concentration of sodium chloride and magnesium sulphate. Sodium chloride hinders crystallisation of potassium sulphate and other schoenitic potassic salts (schoenite, leonite or lengbenite) from mixed salts while magnesium sulphate hinders recovery of sylvinitic potassic salts (potassium chloride, sodium chloride). Many workers¹ attempted hot extraction techniques for separation of potassic salts from mixed salts from sea bittern and lake brines but no attempt has been reported to separate schoenitic potassic salts and sylvinitic potassic salts from the same mixed salts by hot extraction techniques.

Taking in view the fact that there is vast difference in solubilities of sodium chloride and potassium chloride at high and low temperatures and also the fact that potassium schoenite is predominately formed at low temperature, an attempt has been made in this study to separate major portion of sodium chloride by heating the mixed salts with water at high temperature. Also on cooling this supersaturated solution, sylvinitic salts separate first till a specific temperature and later on magnesium sulphate, potassium sulphate starts precipitating and dominating the separated salts. This specific temperature can act as a boundary-line in separation of sylvinitic potassic salts and schoenitic potassic salts from the mixed salts. Since potassium schoenite is unstable above 25° so temperatures of 26, 30, 34 and 38° have been selected for this study.

Experimental

Four sets (Set I-IV) of 2 kg each of the mixed salts from Tsokar lake brine (having composition of NaCl, 44.80%; MgSO₄, 18.63%; K₂SO₄, 4.95% and KCl, 17.92%) were ground to pass 12 mesh sieve. To each of the above sample boiling water (2.5 dm³) was added and the solution digested for 30 min on

a hot-plate (when temperature of solution remained at 95°). It was then filtered hot giving residue R and filtrate. The filtrate was cooled to 26, 30, 34 and 38° in sets I to IV respectively. At this stage the salt crop separated out was collected and designated as IA to IVA. The filtrate obtained after separating salt crop-A was then cooled from their respective temperatures to 20° when another salt crop was separated and designated as IB to IVB.

Three sets (Set V-VII) of 2 kg each of mixed salt were processed as above and cooled from 95 to 34° when crops VA to VIIA were collected and then cooled from 34 to 20° to obtain crops VB to VIIB.

Crops VA to VIIA (100 g each) were digested separately with water (90 ml; sufficient to dissolve potassium chloride) at 95° and digested till a thick slurry was formed. It was cooled to 20° and filtered. The crops were designated VAW to VIIAW. Similarly, crops VB to VIIB were digested separately with water (90 ml) for 30 min and cooled to 20° and filtered. The crops were designated as VBW and VIIBW. In this study the filtration equipment was pre-maintained at the temperature of filtration.

Salt crops obtained in this study were analysed after air-drying by usual method², sulphate by barium chloride method, chloride by silver nitrate method, sodium and potassium by flame photometer and magnesium by EDTA method. Chemical composition of the salt crops were worked out as earlier³ (Tables 1 and 2).

Results and Discussion

On cooling the solution from 95 to 38° or 34°, the salts separated are of typical sylvinitic type having negligible amount of magnesium sulphate (1.98 and 1.75%) IA-IVA, while on cooling the solution from 95 to 30° or 26° the salts separated have high concentration of magnesium sulphate

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TABLE 1—CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE SALT FRACTIONS*

Set no.	Temp. of separation °C	KCl	K ₂ SO ₄	MgSO ₄	NaCl	MgCl ₂
IA	26	47.68	9.13	19.84	8.90	—
B	20	9.32	37.24	24.75	6.35	—
IIA	30	55.86	4.90	13.85	7.15	—
B	20	8.20	35.65	27.22	5.30	—
IIIA	34	76.84	—	1.75	10.93	0.19
B	20	9.47	34.74	23.73	5.84	—
IVA	38	76.84	—	1.98	11.94	—
B	20	6.48	32.53	28.75	13.72	—

*Quantity of mixed salts taken in each set=2 kg.

TABLE 2—CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE SALT FRACTIONS EXTRACTED*

Set no.	KCl	K ₂ SO ₄	MgSO ₄	NaCl	MgCl ₂	Schoenite K ₂ SO ₄ .MgSO ₄ . 6H ₂ O
VA	74.36	—	3.13	8.13	2.50	—
B	10.75	32.06	26.48	6.35	—	74.06
AW	98.20	—	—	1.28	—	—
BW	—	71.30	7.90	2.80	—	19.35
VIA	76.46	—	0.96	13.41	0.62	—
B	4.38	40.66	26.72	3.82	—	89.35
AW	97.82	—	—	1.90	—	—
BW	—	70.86	7.91	1.40	—	19.35
VIIA	68.85	—	4.73	10.42	3.10	—
B	11.46	34.82	23.11	5.60	—	77.29
AW	98.00	—	—	1.52	—	—
BW	—	72.22	7.67	2.55	—	18.77

*Quantity of mixed salt taken to extract A and B=2 kg; quantity of A and B fractions taken to extract AW and BW=0.1 kg.

(13.85 and 19.84%) rendering it unsuitable for further processing. Potassium sulphate is not precipitated at 38 or 34° and remains low at 30 and 26° (4.90 and 9.13%).

Similarly, on cooling the solution from 34 to 20° the salts separated are of typical schoenite type (Table 1) with least sodium chloride (5.84%) in it. There is an increase in sodium chloride contents (13.72%) if the solution is cooled from 38 to 20° giving composition similar to the mixed salts (set IVB). It is evident from Table 1 that there is not much of change in sodium chloride contents, if solution is cooled from 34° or lower than 34 to 20° (IB–IIIB). This gives a clear understanding that mixed salts can be separated into two fractions, viz. sylvinitic fraction and schoenitic fraction, if its solution at 95° is cooled to 34° to separate out sylvinitic salt fraction first and later the solution may be cooled to 20° to separate out schoenitic salt fraction.

The residue (R) left after extraction of potassic salts at 95° has 61–64% sodium chloride which amounts to 16–17% out of the total sodium chloride percent in the mixed salts. The magnesium sulphate separated alongwith the residue amounts to 6–7%. Separation of both sodium chloride and magnesium sulphate (in residue) leaves the solution well-suited for further extraction of potassic salts.

The filtrate after removal of the residue, having high concentration of potassium ions when cooled from 95 to 34° in sets V, VI and VII (Table 2), separates A-fractions having mostly potassium chloride and sodium chloride owing to their supersaturation. The potassium chloride and sodium chloride contents in these fractions vary slightly and their proportions are 74.36 and 8.13% in VA, 76.46 and 13.41% in VIA, and 68.85 and 10.42% in VIIA, respectively. The magnesium sulphate and magnesium chloride contents in these fractions are comparatively very low (3.13, 2.50; 0.96, 0.62; and 4.73, 3.10%) and is due to co-precipitation or getting trapped of the adhering mother liquor in the salt fraction.

The filtrates after separation of A-fractions in sets V, VI and VII, have high concentrations of magnesium and sulphate ions. When cooled from 34 to 20°, the crystallisation behaviour shifts from sylvinitic deposition to schoenitic deposition. The salt fraction-B in sets V, VI and VII have 74.06, 89.35 and 77.29% schoenite respectively. The schoenite in these sets is having stoichiometric proportions of potassium sulphate and magnesium sulphate with 2.00 and 1.40% excess of potassium sulphate in VIB and VIIB respectively. This gives a clear understanding of the fact that schoenite

forms a perfect equimolar proportion⁴. The only undesirable salt in B-fraction is sodium chloride but is far less than the amount that can hinder precipitation of purer salt or double salt by further processing. The concentrations of sodium chloride in VB, VIB and VIIB are 6.35, 3.82 and 5.60% respectively, while potassium chloride contents are 10.75, 4.38 and 11.46% respectively, which enhance the overall K₂O contents of the salts separated.

Potassium chloride: On reprocessing fraction-A of sets V, VI and VII, potassium chloride of about 58% (AW) is obtained (Table 2). This agrees with the similar attempts by the earlier workers⁶ that on cooling a solution of sodium chloride and potassium chloride from 100 to 20°, pure potassium chloride is obtained. In AW-V, VI and VII, the purity of potassium chloride is 98.20, 97.82 and 98.00% respectively, with sodium chloride 1.28, 1.90 and 1.52% respectively. This is due to very little difference in solubilities of sodium chloride at high and low temperatures compared to that of potassium chloride. Since sodium chloride limit acceptable in potassic fertilisers⁶ is 3%, so the product AW, is well-suited as fertiliser.

Potassium sulphate and schoenite: Fraction-B is a high quality schoenite, but the presence of 6.35, 3.82 and 5.60% sodium chloride in VB, VIB and VIIB respectively, renders it unfit as fertiliser. On reprocessing fraction-B the double sulphate of potassium and magnesium obtained has K₂SO₄ and MgSO₄ as 71.30 and 7.91, 70.86 and 7.91, and 72.22 7.67% in BW-V, VI and VII respectively, with sodium chloride 2.80, 1.40 and 2.55% percent respectively (Table 2). The drastic increase in potassium sulphate contents from B to BW is due to the action of water on potassium chloride and magnesium sulphate giving rise to potassium sulphate and highly soluble magnesium chloride. The decrease in sodium chloride content is due to its solubility in mother liquor. Besides, the magnesium chloride and sodium chloride concentrations in mother liquor in turn decrease the solubility of schoenite and potassium sulphate. The product BW obtained after reprocessing is a mixture of potassium sulphate and schoenite. In BW V, VI

and VII, the potassium sulphate and potassium schoenite contents are 59.86 and 19.35, 59.42 and 19.35, and 61.12 and 18.77% respectively. Since sodium chloride contents are never more than 2.80% (Table 2), it makes the product BW well-suited as potassium-magnesium fertiliser with high contents of K₂O (38.30–39.15%) than in simple schoenite (23.39%).

The filtrate left after removal of A- and B-fractions has composition: Na, 10–11; K, 3–4; Mg, 2; chloride, 18–19; sulphate, 9–10%, which is similar to the composition of the mixed salts and thus can be recycled. The study concludes that mixed salts from Tsokar lake can be separated into sylvinitic and schoenitic potassic salt fractions at 34°. Sylvinitic fraction on processing gives potassium chloride of 98% purity and schoenitic fraction on processing gives a mixture of potassium sulphate and schoenite having 38–39% K₂O and < 3% sodium chloride, that makes both the products AW and BW suitable as potassic fertilisers.

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